

Student Satisfaction on Enrollment Services towards a Proposed Manual of Operation

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Index Terms:

student Expectation, Perception, and Satisfaction, Enrollment Services, SERVQUAL Model, Enrollment Procedure, Higher Education, Institutional Improvement

Abstract. This study examined student satisfaction with enrollment services at XYZ College as a basis for developing an enhanced enrollment procedure. Grounded in the SERVQUAL Model, Expectation Confirmation Theory, and the American Customer Satisfaction Index framework, the research focused on five dimensions of service quality: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. A descriptive-correlational quantitative research design with impact analysis was employed. Data were collected from 382 college students during the Academic Year 2025–2026 using a validated self-constructed questionnaire. Statistical tools included weighted mean, Wilcoxon signed-rank test, Spearman’s rank correlation, and multiple linear regression. Findings revealed that students generally had high expectations, perceptions, and satisfaction levels across all service quality dimensions. However, significant gaps were identified between expectations and actual experiences, indicating areas needing improvement. Results further showed a significant positive relationship between students’ perceptions of enrollment services and their overall satisfaction. Among the dimensions, responsiveness, reliability, and assurance emerged as strong predictors of satisfaction, while tangibility and empathy showed varying levels of influence. Moreover, the combined effect of service quality dimensions significantly influenced student satisfaction. The study concludes that improving enrollment services requires a holistic, student-centered approach that integrates efficiency, accuracy, responsiveness, and effective communication. Based on the findings, a proposed operations manual was developed to enhance enrollment procedures by addressing identified gaps and aligning services with student expectations. The results contribute to the improvement of institutional practices and provide a framework for strengthening student satisfaction, retention, and overall service quality in higher education.

Introduction

Enrollment is a critical process in higher education because it allows students to officially begin their academic journey. A smooth and efficient system reflects the institution’s commitment to quality service. However, many schools still face challenges in making enrollment accessible, transparent, and efficient. Student satisfaction during enrollment is not only about convenience but also about building trust and confidence. Therefore, reviewing current procedures and identifying areas for improvement is essential. Globally, student satisfaction in enrollment has become a major concern as institutions compete to attract and retain students. It is considered an important factor in student retention and institutional credibility (Levitz, 2020). According to Tesema and Fathoni (2023), enrollment systems and quality assurance are key to institutional competitiveness. While many schools adopt digital platforms to improve efficiency, some still struggle with slow and complex processes that affect student satisfaction (ICEF Monitor, 2025). In the Philippines, student satisfaction has been influenced by the shift to online and blended learning. Institutions must continuously improve student services to maintain satisfaction (Maslang et al., 2021). Studies also show that innovation and adaptability are important in improving enrollment experiences (Montejo et al., 2025). Additionally, enrollment

experiences can affect students' motivation and overall academic outlook (Lubon et al., 2025). This study aims to evaluate student satisfaction with current enrollment procedures and propose an improved manual of operations. It seeks to identify challenges and best practices to develop a more efficient, transparent, and student-centered system. Thus, the goal is to enhance student experience, build trust, and strengthen institutional competitiveness.

Research Paradigm

Figure 1. The Research Paradigm of the Study

Research Questions:

1. What is the level of expectation on enrollment services among students of XYZ College in terms of: Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, and, Empathy?
2. What is the level of experience on enrollment services among students of XYZ College in terms of the above-mentioned variables?
3. What is the level of satisfaction with enrollment services among the students of XYZ College in terms of the above-mentioned variables?
4. Is there a significant difference in levels of expectation and experience on enrollment services among the students of XYZ College?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the levels of experience and satisfaction with enrollment services among the students of XYZ College?
6. Does the level of experience singly or in combination impact the level of satisfaction with enrollment services among students of XYZ College?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what manual of operations to enrollment services can be proposed to further improve the student enrollment influenced by service quality and satisfaction in the XYZ College?

Methodology

This study used a descriptive correlational quantitative research design with impact analysis. This design was chosen to measure student satisfaction with enrollment services, identify areas for improvement, and examine how students' experiences affect their level of satisfaction. A descriptive correlational design focuses on identifying relationships between variables without manipulating them (Barooah, 2025). It allows researchers to observe how factors are connected in real-life situations. In addition, impact analysis was used to evaluate the possible effects of enrollment services on students. It helps identify potential benefits, risks, and outcomes of decisions (Masterclass, 2022). This method supports better decision-making by anticipating possible issues and improving planning.

The respondents of this study consisted of college students who had recently availed of enrollment services during the Academic Year 2025–2026, of at least one enrollment transaction was considered an eligible respondent. This ensures that all participants had firsthand experience with the enrollment procedures under evaluation. From a total population of 8,627 students, a sample size of 382 was determined using Slovin's Formula, a commonly used statistical tool for estimating sample size when the population is known.

This study utilized a self-made questionnaire. The survey questionnaires were divided into four (4) parts. The first part was focused on the demographic profile of the respondents to identify the group according to age, gender, college programs, and year level at the school. The second part was the level of expectation on enrollment services in XYZ College in terms of the SERVQUAL dimensions (Tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy). The third part was the level of perception on enrollment services in XYZ College in terms of the above-mentioned SERVQUAL dimensions. The fourth

part was the level of satisfaction with enrollment services among the students of XYZ College in terms of the above-mentioned SERVQUAL dimensions.

The primary data for this study were collected from students of XYZ College using a validated survey questionnaire. The survey measured students' expectations, perceptions, and satisfaction with enrollment services in terms of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Before data collection, permission was obtained from the school administration, and ethical standards were followed by including an informed consent form in the survey. The researcher also coordinated with department deans to inform them about the study. Data were collected through face-to-face distribution of printed questionnaires to ensure accessibility and higher participation. Respondents were given enough time to read the consent form and decide voluntarily whether to participate. Only those who agreed proceeded with the survey. The researcher monitored the process to ensure proper distribution and checked all completed questionnaires for accuracy. All data were kept confidential, and no personal information was included, following the Data Privacy Act of 2012. The responses were then encoded, organized, and cleaned for analysis. A statistician applied appropriate statistical methods to ensure accurate results and meaningful conclusions.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Expectation on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Tangibility	3.15	0.486	High
2. Reliability	3.19	0.497	High
3. Responsiveness	3.04	0.515	High
4. Assurance	3.35	0.465	Very High
5. Empathy	3.11	0.536	High
Overall Expectation	3.17	0.435	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Very High, 2.51-3.25 High, 1.76-2.50 – Low, 1.00-1.75 – Very Low

Table 1. The Level of Expectation on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Table 1 summarizes students' expectations of enrollment services at XYZ College across the five SERVQUAL dimensions. The overall expectation mean is 3.17 (SD = 0.435), indicating a generally high and consistent level of expectations. Among the dimensions, Assurance has the highest expectation (M = 3.35, Very High), showing that students strongly value staff competence, professionalism, credibility, and confidentiality. This supports Aristores and Nemiño (2025), who emphasized that assurance builds institutional trust, and Chala (2021), who found it strongly linked to student satisfaction. The remaining dimensions, Reliability (M = 3.19), Tangibility (M = 3.15), Empathy (M = 3.11), and Responsiveness (M = 3.04), are all rated "High." This suggests that students expect accurate, organized, prompt, and considerate services. These align with Nadela et al. (2023) on the importance of physical facilities, Cierva and Malangsa (2021) on accuracy and consistency, and Twum & Peprah (2020) and Mines et al. (2025), who note that responsiveness and empathy are valued but often affected by operational constraints. Overall, students expect consistently high service quality, especially in assurance and reliability, highlighting the importance of competent staff, accurate processes, and professional service delivery (SERVQUAL framework).

The Level of Experience on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Tangibility	3.11	0.537	High
2. Reliability	3.20	0.505	High
3. Responsiveness	3.08	0.524	High
4. Assurance	3.29	0.482	Very High
5. Empathy	3.14	0.55	High
Overall Experience	3.16	0.46	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Very High, 2.51-3.25 High, 1.76-2.50 – Low, 1.00-1.75 – Very Low

Table 2. The Level of Experience on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Table 2 shows students' overall expectations of enrollment services at XYZ College across the five SERVQUAL dimensions. The overall mean is 3.17 (SD = 0.435), indicating consistently high expectations. Assurance has the highest expectation (M = 3.35, Very High), showing that students strongly value staff competence, professionalism, credibility, and confidentiality. This aligns with Aristores and Nemiño (2025), who emphasized that assurance builds institutional trust, and Chala (2021), who found it strongly linked to student satisfaction. The other dimensions—Reliability (M = 3.19), Tangibility (M = 3.15), Empathy (M = 3.11), and Responsiveness (M = 3.04)—are all rated "High." This means students expect accurate, organized, prompt, and considerate services. These findings are supported by Nadela et al. (2023) on the importance of facilities, Cierva and Malangsa (2021) on accuracy and consistency, and Twum & Peprah (2020) and Mines et al. (2025), who note that responsiveness and empathy are important but often affected by service constraints. Overall, students expect high-quality enrollment services, especially in assurance and reliability, emphasizing the need for competent staff and accurate, professional service delivery (SERVQUAL framework).

The Level of Satisfaction on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Tangibility	3.08	0.57	High
2. Reliability	3.20	0.542	High
3. Responsiveness	3.15	0.524	High
4. Assurance	3.27	0.511	Very High
5. Empathy	3.15	0.569	High
Overall Experience	3.16	0.46	High

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Very High, 2.51-3.25 High, 1.76-2.50 – Low, 1.00-1.75 – Very Low

Table 3 The Level of Satisfaction on Enrollment Services among Students of XYZ College

Table 3 summarizes students' satisfaction with enrollment services at XYZ College across the five SERVQUAL dimensions. The overall satisfaction mean is 3.17 (SD = 0.493), indicating a generally high and consistent level of satisfaction. Assurance is the highest-rated dimension (M = 3.27, Very High), showing strong satisfaction with staff professionalism, competence, and trustworthiness. This supports Aristores and Nemiño (2025), who emphasized that assurance builds trust and satisfaction, and Chala (2021), who identified it as a key predictor of satisfaction in administrative services. The remaining dimensions—Reliability (M = 3.20), Responsiveness (M = 3.15), Empathy (M = 3.15), and Tangibility (M = 3.08)—are all rated "High." This indicates satisfaction with accurate services, prompt assistance, supportive interactions, and physical facilities. These findings align with Nadela et al. (2023) on the role of facilities, Cierva and Malangsa (2021) on accuracy and consistency, Twum & Peprah (2020) and Ocampo & Salazar (2025) on responsiveness and communication, and Rashid et al. (2021) and Yeaman (2020) on empathy and student support. Overall, students are consistently satisfied with enrollment services, especially in assurance, highlighting the importance of competent staff and reliable, student-centered service delivery.

The difference in levels of expectation and experience on enrollment services among the students of XYZ College.

Measures	Mean	SD	W	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Expectation	3.17	0.435	73290	<.001	Reject Ho	Significant
Experience	3.16	0.460				

Effect Size: 1.0 Shapiro Wilk W = 0.977 p < 0.001

Table 4. The difference in levels of expectation and experience on enrollment services among the students of XYZ College.

Table 4 compares students' expectations and actual experiences of enrollment services at XYZ College. The results show almost similar mean scores for expectation (M = 3.17) and experience (M = 3.16), both indicating high levels. However, the Wilcoxon test shows a significant difference (W = 73,290, p < .001), so the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that even if the difference in means is small, students still experienced a mismatch between what they expected and what they received. The large sample size (N = 377) may have contributed to the detection of this significant difference. The large effect size (1.0) also shows that the gap is meaningful in practice, not just statistically. Overall, the findings suggest that some student expectations were not fully met, consistent with SERVQUAL theory, which explains that gaps occur when

expected service quality is higher than actual delivery. This is supported by studies noting that factors such as digital systems, workload, and staff capacity can create service gaps (Harahap et al., 2024; Camilleri, 2021).

The relationship between the levels of experience and satisfaction with enrollment services among the students of XYZ College.

Perception	Satisfaction	Rho	df	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Tangibility	Tangibility	0.805	377	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Reliability	0.688	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Responsiveness	0.686	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Assurance	0.607	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Empathy	0.635	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Overall		0.684	379	< .001	Reject H₀₁	Significant
Reliability	Tangibility	0.759	378	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Reliability	0.794	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Responsiveness	0.752	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Assurance	0.721	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Empathy	0.688	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Overall		0.743	380	< .001	Reject H₀₁	Significant
Responsiveness	Tangibility	0.781	377	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Reliability	0.780	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Responsiveness	0.819	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Assurance	0.684	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Empathy	0.760	379	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Overall		0.765	379	< .001	Reject H₀₁	Significant
Assurance	Tangibility	0.681	378	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Reliability	0.712	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Responsiveness	0.68	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Assurance	0.762	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Empathy	0.666	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Overall		0.700	380	< .001	Reject H₀₁	Significant
Empathy	Tangibility	0.716	378	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Reliability	0.744	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Responsiveness	0.776	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Assurance	0.669	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
	Empathy	0.793	380	< .001	Reject H ₀₁	Significant
Overall		0.740	380	< .001	Reject H₀₁	Significant

Note: Significant if $p < 0.05$

Table 5. The relationship between the levels of experience and satisfaction with enrollment services among the students of XYZ College.

Table 5 shows the relationship between students' experiences and satisfaction with enrollment services at XYZ College using Spearman's rho. All SERVQUAL dimensions have significant positive relationships with satisfaction ($p < 0.001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. All correlations are strong. Tangibility ($\rho = 0.684$), Reliability ($\rho = 0.743$), Responsiveness ($\rho = 0.765$), Assurance ($\rho = 0.700$), and Empathy ($\rho = 0.740$) all show that better experiences are associated with higher satisfaction. The strongest relationships are found in Responsiveness ($\rho = 0.765$) and Reliability ($\rho = 0.743$), indicating these are the most influential factors. Overall, the results show that improvements in physical facilities, accuracy, prompt service, staff competence, and empathy all contribute to higher student satisfaction. This supports findings by Wood

(2024), Abucayon et al. (2025), and Aristores and Nemiño (2025), who emphasized that timely, accurate, and professional service delivery strongly enhances student satisfaction and trust. In summary, student satisfaction is strongly linked to service experience, and improving any SERVQUAL dimension is likely to increase overall satisfaction.

Impact of Experience Dimensions on Students' Satisfaction: Multiple Regression Analysis

Variable	Estimate	SE	t	p	Interpretation
Intercept	0.101	0.0725	1.4	0.163	
Tangibility	0.108	0.0322	3.36	<.001	significant predictor
Reliability	0.164	0.0396	4.14	<.001	significant predictor
Responsiveness	0.289	0.0383	7.54	<.001	significant predictor
Assurance	0.184	0.0341	5.39	<.001	Significant predictor
Empathy	0.227	0.0313	7.25	<.001	significant predictor

Model Statistics R² = .844, F = 404, p < .001

Table 6 Impact of Experience Dimensions on Students' Satisfaction: Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 6 presents the results of the multiple regression analysis on whether the five SERVQUAL dimensions—tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy—predict student satisfaction at XYZ College. The model is highly significant ($F = 404, p < .001$) and explains 84.4% of the variance in satisfaction ($R^2 = .844$), showing that student experience strongly determines satisfaction. All five dimensions are significant predictors ($p < .001$). Responsiveness is the strongest predictor ($\beta = 0.289$), followed by empathy ($\beta = 0.227$) and assurance ($\beta = 0.184$), indicating that prompt service, understanding staff, and professional behavior are most important to students. Reliability ($\beta = 0.164$) also contributes significantly, while tangibility ($\beta = 0.108$) is the weakest predictor but still significant. Overall, the results show that all service dimensions influence satisfaction, with responsiveness, empathy, and assurance having the greatest impact. This supports Twum & Peprah (2020) and Ocampo & Salazar (2025), who found that timely and efficient service improves satisfaction, Rashid et al. (2021), who emphasized empathy and professionalism, and Cierva and Malangsa (2021), who highlighted the importance of accuracy and consistency in building trust.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The findings of the study reveal that students of XYZ College have high expectations for enrollment services, particularly in terms of efficiency, reliability, and responsiveness. Their actual experiences are generally positive, showing that the institution is able to deliver acceptable service quality through its systems and personnel. However, there is still a significant gap between expectations and actual experiences, meaning that services do not fully meet what students anticipate. The study confirms that students' satisfaction is strongly influenced by how services are delivered, especially in terms of communication, speed, accuracy, and staff interaction, and that their direct experiences play a major role in shaping satisfaction. Overall, satisfaction depends on the quality of service across responsiveness, assurance, empathy, reliability, and tangibility, highlighting the need for continuous improvement through standardized processes, better staff training, and a more student-centered enrollment system to ensure more consistent and higher-quality service delivery.

The XYZ College administration, Registrar's Office, Human Resource Office, and Facilities Management are recommended to improve enrollment services by prioritizing faster and more responsive assistance, strengthening staff competence and professionalism, and enhancing reliability, empathy, and assurance through continuous training and better communication. Physical facilities should also be improved, as tangibility received lower ratings, to create a more comfortable and organized enrollment environment. The institution should establish a Quality Assurance Office and implement regular monitoring, feedback systems, and service evaluations to ensure consistent service quality and to help close the gap between students' expectations and actual experiences. Continuous process improvements and standardized procedures are also needed to ensure more efficient and student-centered services. Overall, the goal is to enhance student satisfaction by improving actual service experiences while maintaining strong performance across all service dimensions, and future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar studies in other institutions and explore additional factors such as digital systems, institutional policies, and student outcomes like retention and performance.

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Competing Interests Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this article.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.